

CA20104 – Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age (PhysAgeNet)

Deliverable D4.2.

D4.2. Stakeholder Analysis Matrix: list of stakeholders, their interests and influence on the topic

Contributors

Working Group 4

Signe Tomsone (Associate Professor/WG4 leader), Jonathan Gómez-Raja (Chief Scientific Officer/WG4 vice-leader), David Paar (Associate Professor/WG4 member)

1. INTRODUCTION

PhysAgeNet (COST Action CA20104) is a European network focused on promoting evidence-based physical activity in older adults. The network integrates interdisciplinary research and practice across Europe, aiming to enhance health outcomes and reduce inactivity-related burdens through innovative ICT solutions and open data frameworks.

Stakeholders are parties that will be affected by operations, objectives and results of the network. Stakeholders that are relevant for the network are categorised and mapped according to several different perspectives including their geographical broadness, domains, type of activity, interest in the results, and level of influence.

The Science Communication Plan of the PhysAgeNet defined the aim of all communication, dissemination and valorisation activities: to have evidence-based approaches for physical activity in old age adopted by all relevant stakeholders.

As a **main target audience** were emphasized any experts aiming to prescribe and/or implement physical activity plans for older adults e.g.

- Sports and Exercise Scientists
- Physiotherapists
- General practitioners (GPs))

Secondary target audiences were all the rest of stakeholders that actively or passively involved in the field of physical activity and exercise in older adults, e.g.:

- Scientists/researchers in the field of sports and exercise science, physiotherapy, gerontology, geriatrics/medicine, gerontechnology, rehabilitation sciences and other related fields
- General public and especially (older) adults (as in the lay audience at which the evidence-based physical activity practised should be applied to)
- Policy makers at national/local (e.g. ministries of health, ministries of sport, sport commissions, national sports organisations, non-governmental associations (NGOs), research institutions/universities, health insurance companies) and international level (e.g. European Commission: Directorate-General for Education, Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety, Youth, Sport and Culture, EU Sports Forum and other Health-related initiatives)
- Funders at national (e.g. German Research Foundation, German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, Swiss National Science Foundation, Italian Ministry of University and Research) and international level (e.g. Horizon Europe, European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST))
- Professional Associations (e.g. American College of Sports Medicine, International Society for Physical Activity and Health)
- Peer-review scientific journals, e.g. European Review of Aging and Physical Activity (BMC Central), Journal of Aging and Physical Activity (Human Kinetics), Frontiers in Sports and Active Living (Frontiers Ltd), Journal of Physical Activity and Health (Human Kinetics)

Tertiary target audiences were:

- Media (at national and international level)
- Small-medium enterprises (SMEs) in the field of physical activity and exercise in older adults, e.g. SMEs that provide tools for the delivery of PA and exercise

PhysAgeNet participated in Horizon Results Booster (HRB) Module A – Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy, forming a Project Group (PG) with DE-PASS and PROGRAMMING (2024). **A stakeholder mapping was part of the process** identifying priority audiences: researchers, healthcare professionals, policy experts, and older adults

The communication, dissemination and valorisation for various stakeholders for the PhysAgeNet and engagement status by the end of network are identified below.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Researchers & Academia

<p>How stakeholders can benefit from the network</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The increased exchange of knowledge between researchers, clinicians, trainers. • Data platform and tools allow researchers to access valuable data on physical activity interventions for older adults and leverage it for their own studies. • The network provides opportunities for collaboration on new research projects and knowledge sharing through workshops and discussions.
<p>Engagement</p>	<p>Engaged on a consortium and network level. Needs to be informed outside the network on results achieved.</p>

2.2. Policy experts and Activists

<p>How stakeholders can benefit from the network</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy experts and activists can significantly strengthen their advocacy efforts and contribute to the development and implementation of effective policies that promote physical activity and healthy aging for older adults. • The network provides a platform for policy experts and activists to connect with researchers and practitioners working on physical activity promotion. This fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing, leading to more effective policy solutions.
<p>Engagement</p>	<p>Supportive (Aware of project & impacts and supportive to change).</p>

2.3. Healthcare Professionals

How stakeholders can benefit from the network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical guidance for Healthcare Professionals and consolidated research information to design optimal, safe, feasible and effective PA programs for various target group. • Increase PA uptake while improving the experience of healthcare professionals and patients because use of the rehearsal strategies. • Competencies skill-up with geriatric medicine and physical activities programs
Engagement	Needs to be informed on results achieved.

2.4. Policy makers and public health institutions

How stakeholders can benefit from the network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers benefits from easy-to-digest, trustful joint recommendations document that will help shape better policies and programmes and dissemination material
Engagement	Needs to be informed on results achieved. and their potential impact.

2.5. Older people and their carers

How stakeholders can benefit from the network results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The network provides evidence-based information and well-trained practitioners across all the spectrum of health care services • The network results help to adopt more active lifestyle.
Engagement to date	Needs to be informed on results achieved. and their potential impact.

2.5. Barriers to dissemination

Id	Stakeholder group	Description	Considerations
B1	Researchers & Academia	Multiple databases and resources	The abundance of databases and resources across various platforms can hinder accessibility for target audiences and researchers alike.
B2	Policy experts and activists	Limited time and resources	Research findings might be presented in technical language, making it difficult for policy experts and activists without a scientific background to understand and utilise the information effectively. Furthermore, policy experts and activists often work under tight deadlines and may lack the resources or time to delve into complex research reports. User-friendly formats might help disseminate the results.
B3	Healthcare Professionals	Reliance on academic journals, while important, doesn't reach practitioners and policymakers who need actionable findings.	Moving beyond traditional academic publications to reach a broader audience is recommendable. Complement peer-reviewed papers with user-friendly formats, such as factsheets, infographics, and short video explainers. Develop a template for a concise and easy-to-read report summarizing key findings and recommendations applicable to diverse contexts. This will raise awareness and improve accessibility of research for various stakeholders.
B4	Policy makers and public health institutions	Unaware on results of the network.	Network can act more effectively in terms of reaching broader audiences both in terms of policy makers, medical experts, and patients.
B5	Older people	Outreach barriers	Develop a targeted social media campaign specifically aimed at the 60+ demographic. Craft clear and engaging messages with actionable recommendations to reach this audience effectively on relevant platforms.

2.7. Dissemination channels

	Researchers & Academia	Policy experts and activists	Healthcare Professionals	Policy makers and public health institutions
Demos and Videos	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Website and Blogs	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Newsletters		Yes		
Social: LinkedIn	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Press Releases and Kits	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flyers, Banners, Posters				Yes

	Researchers & Academia	Policy experts and activists	Healthcare Professionals	Policy makers and public health institutions
Events and Workshops	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Presentations	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Infographics and Factsheets	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Datasets and insights	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Policy Briefs		Yes		Yes

Note: In bold highlighted dissemination channels used by network.

ANNEX 1 EXAMPLES OF DISSEMINATION NETWORKS

The information added is based on the Stakeholder matrix (link below):

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1EX70nuSDt9WpWglqkaF07y5AGqjrz0v6aafZyhELIM/edit?gid=0#gid=0>

N	Stakeholder	Organisation	Type	Contacts
1.	Researchers & Academia, Policy experts & Activists, Healthcare Professionals, Policy makers and public health institutions	EGRAPA – The European Group for Research on Aging and Physical Activity	Related Initiative	Website: https://www.egrappa.org/
2.	Researchers & Academia	European Review of Aging and Physical Activity (EURAPA) (BMC Central)	Journal	Website: https://eurapa.biomedcentral.com/
3.	Researchers & Academia	Journal of Aging and Physical Activity (Human Kinetics)	Journal	

N	Stakeholder	Organisation	Type	Contacts
4.	Researchers & Academia	Frontiers in Sports and Active Living (Frontiers Ltd)	Journal	Website:
5.	Researchers & Academia	Journal of Physical Activity and Health (Human Kinetics)	Journal	Website:
6.	All	PA4AGE	Erasmus+ Project	Website: https://pa4age-project.eu/
7.	Older people	AGE	International organization	Website: https://www.age-platform.eu/
8.	All	Determinants of Physical Activities in Settings (DEPASS)	COST Action (CA19101)	Website: https://depass.eu/
9.	All	PRoMoting GeRiAtric Medicine in countries where it is still eMergING (PROGRAMMING)	COST Action (CA21122)	Website: https://cost-programming.eu/